

MAPPING THE SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ON DATA JOURNALISM AND OPEN DATA

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Keywords: Open Data; Data Journalism; Systematic Literature Review

1. Introduction

During the past decade, the available information has increased exponentially from governmental and private sources. On one side governments all over the world are releasing data with the goal to increase their transparency, provide better services to their citizens, and enhance overall efficiency. On the other side, the rise of social media introduced an era of abundant information and instant news propagation like nothing experienced before. Journalists are called to evaluate and process an immense volume of information in this sifting field of direct news and novel emerging data sources(Gray et al., 2012).

In the past journalists were unaccustomed to the use of freely available data in vast quantities and although the use of data, especially in the field of investigative journalism, is not novel the plethora of technological advantages(Calvo-Rubio and Ufarte-Ruiz, 2021; Hassan and Albayari, 2022) provide them with the ability to present a compelling story in a different scale in the data that had been processed and in the potential to visualize and therefore communicate it more compellingly. But these capabilities require specialized technical skills(Veglis and Bratsas, 2017) by the journalists and this can be an important impediment to their utilization of open data.

Data journalism(Bhaskaran et al., 2022; Calvo-Rubio and Ufarte-Ruiz, 2021) and open data(Hurbean et al., 2021; Ismail and Yusof, 2022; Zhang et al., 2018) themselves are well-researched fields in academia but the combination of these two fields is still limited. In this paper, we present a mapping of academic endeavours in the field of data journalism with the use of open data aiming not only to categorize the developments in the field but also to identify benefits and barriers.

2. Methodology

The method used for the analysis of the literature and the identification of topics is a systematic literature review(Okoli, 2015; Xiao and Watson, 2019) (SLR). In the following parts of the chapter, we will analyze the steps of the protocol.

Since this research aims to analyse the progression of publication on data journalism with the use of open data one research question was formulated and refined in greater detail with an analysis framework matrix (**Table 1**).

RQ1: “How the research literature on data journalism with the use of open data is developing, and what are the most significant benefits and barriers encountered in published papers?”

Table 1. Analysis framework matrix

Category	Sub-Category	Description
1. Developing of open data research	1.1 Year of the publication	The year when the paper was published
	1.2 Country of the institution	The country where the institution that conducted the research is based
	1.3 Country of research	The country where the research was conducted
2. The topic of the research	2.1 Discipline of research	Use of the Science-Metrix disciplinary classifications
	2.2 Topic of the research	Defines the area explored in the publication
	2.3 Topic of data used	Defines the type of data used in the research (Education, Health, Transportation, Geospatial, etc)
3. Methodologies of the research	3.1 Methodologies for data collection	Survey, Interview, Observation, Literature review, Case study
	3.2 Methodology to analyse data	Statistical analysis, Meta-analysis, Thematic analysis, Content analysis
4. Results of the papers	4.1 Benefits	
	4.2 Barriers	

During the initial search of the research, we defined the keyword query that was used and concluded as “Data journalism” AND “Open Data”. The query was used to filter out publications in the title, abstract and keywords on four scientific databases, the databases used are IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Scopus.

Initially from these databases were returned 68 publications, the initial exclusion criteria on that step were only the language of publication, and therefore from the 68 publications, we narrowed down the scope of the research to 55, and after the removal of the duplicate documents we ended up in 36.

During the collection of the papers, we were unable to find three, and three more were excluded from the research during the title and abstract filtering therefore the final amount of publications that are examined in this research is 30.

3. Results

The research is still undergoing and therefore in this chapter we will present some preliminary results for the first two categories of the analysis framework. During the research on open data and data journalism, the first step according to the analysis framework is to identify how this particular field is developing. Therefore we collected the data for the year of the publication, the country of the institution that conducted the research country where the research was conducted in the cases where that was applicable.

3.1. Developing open data research

In this part of the research we are examining the development of the field over the previous years and the topography of the publications. In particular, the countries where the institutions conducted these researches are based. In the future, we will continue with the identification of the countries where these researches were conducted.

3.1.1. Year of the publication

The reason for incorporating the year of publication is to identify the quantitative progression of publications in the field. The interesting observation from the data that are presented in **Figure 1** is that we can see an overall decline in publications since their pick in 2016; Although the open governmental data are increasing (Çaldağ and Gökalp, 2022) the latest bibliometric review for academic publication on open data (Zhang et al., 2018) incorporated data from 2016 and before so we can not be sure that this decline is an emerging trend in the field of open data in general or specific in the use of open data in data journalism.

3.1.2. Country of the institution

The country of the institution is an important factor to identify the countries that are interested in the use of open data in data journalism. As is displayed in **Figure 2** we can observe the dominance of the European Union with 25 publications and the US with 6 publications in the research field. The other countries that do not belong to these groups are the United Kingdom(4), Russia(2), Brazil(1), India(1), Canada(1), Bahrain(1), Switzerland(1), and Palestine(1).

Figure 1. Publications per year

Figure 2. Country of Institution

3.2. Research Topic

In the second part of the research to identify and examine the topic of the research that has been conducted in the field we extracted from the publications the discipline of the research. And we will continue with the purpose that the research, and the topic of the data that has been used where that can be identified.

3.2.1. Research Discipline

The publications were identified to be from different and several academic fields and we had to identify a methodology that can incorporate a wide range of disciplines. Therefore to identify the disciplinary classifications (Sile et al., 2021) of this research we used the Science-Metrix classification for journals since it covers the above-mentioned needs of this research. Although we were unable to identify the discipline of three from the selected publications. The Science-Metrix split classification into three levels and contains 43 categories in the third, we present the finding in that level.

The majority of the publications are in Communication and Media Studies (14) and after that, Information Systems (5), and Artificial Intelligence and Image Processing (4). Overall we can see that the research is balanced between hard and soft science with the technological fields covering 43% of the publications. The data from the classification of the selected publications are presented in **Figure 3** and **Figure 4**.

Figure 3. Disciplinary Classification of publications

3.2.2. Research Topic

After we surveyed all the selected publications we compiled a list of topics that were covered by each research, these topics are presented in **Table 2** with here description. Most publications are focused on the technical aspect and especially on the solutions and tools available in the utilisation of open data by data journalists, this trend indicates a gap in the existing technology and the creation of value from the journalistic community. The percentage of topics is consistent with the classification from the journals since the same percentage can be identified in the technological field. One more interesting observation is the broad field that Communication and Media studies contain, in the topic classification this discipline is split into eight categories.

Table 2. Topic Classification and Description

Topic	Description
Legislation comparison	Examine the impact that different legislations have on data available to journalists.
Technological impact	Explore the impact that new technologies have on the field of data journalism.
Technological solution	Present an abstract technical solution that can be implemented also in different cases
Technological tool	Present the use of a particular technical tool.
Cooperation	Investigate the cooperation between data journalists and other professions closely related to the open data field.
Usage of open data	Evaluates the use of open data by data journalists.
Data journalism Practices	Survey the work of data journalists.
User participation	Investigate the participation of the audience in the creation of open data.
Communication models	Examine different communication models for the dissemination of news.
Education	Identify the educational needs and opportunities in data journalism.
Digital skills	Examine the digital skills needed for the utilisation of open data.

Figure 4. Topic Classification per publication

4. Conclusion

In the exploration of the use of open data in data journalism we are conducting a systematic literature review of the published research on the topic. Our results until now are showing a decrease in the yearly publications and the dominance of the European Union and the US in the field with the majority of the research publication being from institutions in these two areas. Also in the topics that have been researched, we discovered that are balanced between social and technical, publications.

Since the research is undergoing we still have complete the analysis of the publication to determine the countries where these researches were conducted. Furthermore, the methodologies that have been used for the collection and analysis of the data have to be ascertained, and finally, the benefits and barriers of these publications have to be discovered.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge the financial support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 955569. The research was partially funded by TODO project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857592.

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